

IC Modelling and Analysis in Geotechnical Engineering

Model 18

Contents:

IC MAGE M18 is a user-defined model for PLAXIS, developed using the IC MAGE UMIP framework. The model builds upon the SANICLAY model proposed by Dafalias et al. (2006) and incorporates bounding surface formulation. It features both isotropic and kinematic hardening of the bounding surface, which retains the same elliptical shape as the Modified Cam-Clay yield surface. Additional components include small strain stiffness and two different degradation mechanisms, i.e., damage, and destructuration, the latter coupled with an activation mechanism. These components can be selectively activated to reproduce specific features of the clay response under monotonic and cyclic loading conditions.

Disclaimer:

IC MAGE soil models undergo extensive testing and validation but can never be guaranteed to be free of errors. IC MAGE soil models are employed at the users' own risk and the authors of these models cannot be held responsible or liable for any errors arising from their application.

Document history:

Date	Revision	
2025-09-05	1.0	Initial publication

How to cite:

Palmieri, F, Taborda, DMG (2025) "IC MAGE Model 18 – A SANICLAY model with bounding surface for cyclic clay behaviour (Version 1.0)". Zenodo.

doi: [10.5281/zenodo.17063297](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17063297)

Taborda, DMG, Kontoe, S, Tsiampousi, A (2024) "IC MAGE UMIP – universal model interface for PLAXIS (Version 3.6)". Zenodo.

doi: [10.5281/zenodo.13890543](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13890543)

IC MAGE M18

A SANICLAY model with bounding surface for cyclic clay behaviour

PARAMETERS

P1	μ	$-1 < \mu < 0.5$	Poisson's ratio
P2	λ	> 0	Slope of the compression line
P3	κ	> 0	Slope of the swelling lines
P4	M_c	> 0	Stress ratio at critical state in triaxial compression
P5	M_e	> 0	Stress ratio at critical state in triaxial extension
P6	N	> 0	Shape factor for the bounding surface
P7	h_0	> 0	Hardening modulus parameter
P8	a_d	≥ 0	Constant determining evolution of damage
P9	C	≥ 0	Rate of rotational hardening
P10	x	≥ 0	Maximum rotation
P11	s_Y	≥ 1	Size of the elastic region
P12	OCR_1	$< -1, \geq 0$	OCR at the ground surface and up to a depth of d_1
P13	d_1		Depth at which $OCR = OCR_1$
P14	OCR_2		OCR at a depth of d_2
P15	d_2		Depth at which $OCR = OCR_1$
P16	<i>DepthSwitch</i>	0,1,2	Defines vertical direction and coordinate for d_1 and d_2 : global x (0), y (1) or z (2)
P17	e_0 or v_1	$\neq 0$	Initial void ratio (> 0) or volume at 1 kPa for NC samples (< 0)
P18	$K_{min} (FL^{-2})$	≥ 0	Minimum bulk stiffness
P19	<i>PlasticTol</i>	≥ 0	Tolerance for integrating the plastic part
P20	<i>MaxPlasticSteps</i>	≥ 0	Maximum number of steps for integrating plastic part
P21	<i>OutputControl</i>	0,1,2,3,4	Controls the desired output by the model
P22	$p_r (FL^{-2})$	≥ 0	Reference pressure for G_0
P23	A	≥ 0	Elastic stiffness parameter for G_0 (if $P01 = 0$)
P24	n	$0 \leq n < 1$	Elastic stiffness parameter for pressure dependency
P25	m	$0 \leq n < 1$	Elastic stiffness parameter for OCR dependency

P26	k_i	≥ 0	Rate of destructuration
P27	a	≥ 0	Relative contribution between deviatoric and volumetric plastic strain rates
P28	$S_{i,0}$	≥ 1	Sensitivity at initial state
P29	S_b	≥ 1	Sensitivity at destructured state
P30	b_{sr}^{thr}	≥ 1	Activation threshold
P31	<i>EnergyCalc</i>	0,1 → 9, 11 → 19	No energy calculated if 0, see UMIP for other options

DEFAULT VALUES

If set to 0.0, the following defaults values will be assumed:

P19	<i>Plastic_{tot}</i>	1×10^{-4}
P20	<i>MaxPlasticSteps</i>	10000

HARDENING PARAMETERS

HP1	<i>InitVar</i>	Initialisation variable (required by UMIP)
HP2	e_0	Initial void ratio
HP3	e_i	Current void ratio
HP4	p_0	Current size of the bounding surface
HP5	α_{xx}	Axis of the yield surface (x -component)
HP6	α_{yy}	Axis of the yield surface (y -component)
HP7	α_{zz}	Axis of the yield surface (z -component)
HP8	α_{xy}	Axis of the yield surface (xy -component)
HP9	α_{yz}	Axis of the yield surface (yz -component)
HP10	α_{zx}	Axis of the yield surface (xz -component)
HP11	p_c	Mean effective stress at the projection centre
HP12	$S_{xx,c}$	Deviatoric stress state at the projection centre (x -component)
HP13	$S_{yy,c}$	Deviatoric stress state at the projection centre (y -component)
HP14	$S_{zz,c}$	Deviatoric stress state at the projection centre (z -component)
HP15	$S_{xy,c}$	Deviatoric stress state at the projection centre (xy -component)
HP16	$S_{yz,c}$	Deviatoric stress state at the projection centre (yz -component)
HP17	$S_{zx,c}$	Deviatoric stress state at the projection centre (xz -component)
HP18	X	Ratio between stresses at the projection centre and projection point

HP19	d	Damage parameter
HP20	ε_{xx}^p	Plastic strain state (x -component)
HP21	ε_{yy}^p	Plastic strain state (y -component)
HP22	ε_{zz}^p	Plastic strain state (z -component)
HP23	γ_{xy}^p	Plastic strain state (xy -component)
HP24	γ_{yz}^p	Plastic strain state (yz -component)
HP25	γ_{xz}^p	Plastic strain state (xz -component)
HP26	E_d^p	Plastic deviatoric strain
HP27	ε_{vol}^p	Plastic volumetric strain
HP28	G_{tan}	Current elastic shear stiffness
HP29	K_{tan}	Current elastic bulk stiffness
HP30	J	Deviatoric stress (second invariant of stress tensor)
HP31	θ	Lode's angle (third invariant of stress tensor)
HP32	N_{rev}	Number of detected reversals
HP33	\bar{p}	Mean effective stress at the image point
HP34	\bar{s}_{xx}	Deviatoric stress state at the image point (x -component)
HP35	\bar{s}_{yy}	Deviatoric stress state at the image point (y -component)
HP36	\bar{s}_{zz}	Deviatoric stress state at the image point (z -component)
HP37	\bar{s}_{xy}	Deviatoric stress state at the image point (xy -component)
HP38	\bar{s}_{yz}	Deviatoric stress state at the image point (yz -component)
HP39	\bar{s}_{zx}	Deviatoric stress state at the image point (xz -component)
HP40	b	Distance ratio b between image stress and stress state
HP41	Λ	Plastic multiplier
HP42	K_p	Hardening modulus
HP43	ε_d^{p*}	Cumulative destructuration plastic strain
HP44	b_{sr}	Value of distance ratio b at last stress reversal
HP45	$\rho_{0,i}$	Intrinsic size of the bounding surface
HP46 – HP78		Energy calculation (only if <i>P33 EnergyCalc</i> is set to ≥ 1.0)

MODEL FORMULATION

1. Elastic behaviour

1.1 Large strains

The following hypoelastic relations, adopting a non-linear variation of the bulk modulus (K) and a constant Poisson's ratio (μ), are used:

$$K = \nu \cdot \frac{p}{\kappa} \quad (1)$$

$$G = \frac{3K(1 - 2\mu)}{2(1 + \mu)} \quad (2)$$

where $\nu = 1 + e$ is the current specific volume.

1.2 Small strains

If Poisson's ratio is set to zero ($\mu = 0$), the small strain elastic shear modulus is evaluated following Viggiani and Atkinson (1995):

$$\frac{G}{p_r} = A \left(\frac{p}{p_r} \right)^n \cdot R_0^m \quad (3)$$

where A , n and m are material parameters, p_r is the reference pressure so that parameters A , n and m are dimensionless with a value depending on p_r , while $R_0 = p_0/p$ represents OCR in terms of mean pressure.

Furthermore, the elastic bulk modulus is evaluated directly from the slope of the swelling line (P3) as:

$$K = \frac{1 + e}{k} p \quad (4)$$

where e is the current void ratio.

2. Projection rule

The model relies on the behaviour of the soil being assessed at the projection point. This is the 'image' of the current stress state projected onto the bounding surface and can be determined, in terms of isotropic and deviatoric components as:

$$\bar{p} = p_c + b(p - p_c) \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{s} = s_c + b(s - s_c) \quad (6)$$

with the subscript 'c' referring to the stress conditions at the projection centre. The mean effective stress and the deviatoric stress tensor at the projection centre are hardening parameters. Note that, according to this definition of b , the value of this quantity varies between infinity for $p = p_c$ and 1 for $p = \bar{p}$, i.e. reduces gradually as the current stress point approaches the projection point implying $b=1$.

The value of b can be determined following the approach outlined in Seidalinov & Taiebat (2014), taking the positive root of the quadratic equation:

$$Ab^2 + Bb + C = 0 \quad (7)$$

with

$$A = A_1 + \left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2} \alpha : \alpha \right) A_2 \quad (8)$$

$$B = B_1 + \left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2}\boldsymbol{\alpha}:\boldsymbol{\alpha}\right)B_2 \quad (9)$$

$$C = C_1 + \left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2}\boldsymbol{\alpha}:\boldsymbol{\alpha}\right)C_2 \quad (10)$$

and

$$A_1 = \frac{3}{2}(\boldsymbol{s} - \boldsymbol{s}_c):(\boldsymbol{s} - \boldsymbol{s}_c) - 3(p - p_c)[(\boldsymbol{s} - \boldsymbol{s}_c):\boldsymbol{\alpha}] + \frac{3}{2}(p - p_c)^2\boldsymbol{\alpha}:\boldsymbol{\alpha} \quad (11)$$

$$B_1 = 3(\boldsymbol{s} - \boldsymbol{s}_c):\boldsymbol{s}_c - 3[p_c\boldsymbol{s} + (p - 2p_c)\boldsymbol{s}_c]:\boldsymbol{\alpha} + 3p_c(p - p_c)\boldsymbol{\alpha}:\boldsymbol{\alpha} \quad (12)$$

$$C_1 = \frac{3}{2}\boldsymbol{s}_c:\boldsymbol{s}_c - 3p_c\boldsymbol{s}_c:\boldsymbol{\alpha} + \frac{3}{2}p_c^2\boldsymbol{\alpha}:\boldsymbol{\alpha} \quad (13)$$

$$A_2 = (p - p_c)^2 \quad (14)$$

$$B_2 = (2p_c - p_0)(p - p_c) \quad (15)$$

$$C_2 = p_c(p_c - p_0) \quad (16)$$

Therefore:

$$b = \frac{-B \pm \sqrt{B^2 - 4AC}}{2A} \quad (17)$$

and thus:

$$b = \frac{-B + \text{sign}(A) \cdot \sqrt{B^2 - 4AC}}{2A} \quad (18)$$

3. Bounding surface

The bounding surface is given by:

$$F = \frac{3}{2}(\bar{\boldsymbol{s}} - \bar{p}\boldsymbol{\alpha}):(\bar{\boldsymbol{s}} - \bar{p}\boldsymbol{\alpha}) - \left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2}\boldsymbol{\alpha}:\boldsymbol{\alpha}\right) \cdot \bar{p}(p_0 - \bar{p}) = 0 \quad (19)$$

where $p = \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma})/3$ and $\boldsymbol{s} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} - p\boldsymbol{I}$, with the notation \bar{p} and $\bar{\boldsymbol{s}}$ designating these quantities at the projection point, $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ is the tensor defining the axis of the bounding surface, while p_0 is its size.

The gradient of the bounding surface, given that N is assumed to be a constant value (i.e. the shape of the bounding surface in the deviatoric plane is a circle), can be determined using

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} = 3(\bar{\boldsymbol{s}} - \bar{p}\boldsymbol{\alpha}) + \frac{1}{3}\bar{p} \cdot \left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2}\bar{\boldsymbol{r}}:\bar{\boldsymbol{r}}\right)\boldsymbol{I} \quad (20)$$

where

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{r}} = \frac{\bar{\boldsymbol{s}}}{\bar{p}} = \frac{\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} - \bar{p}\boldsymbol{I}}{\bar{p}} \quad (21)$$

4. Plastic potential

The plastic potential is given by a similar shape to that of the plastic potential but with a different value of the inclination:

$$G = \frac{3}{2}(\bar{s} - \bar{p}\alpha) : (\bar{s} - \bar{p}\alpha) - \left(M(\theta)^2 - \frac{3}{2}\alpha : \alpha \right) \cdot \bar{p}(p_0 - \bar{p}) = 0 \quad (22)$$

where $M(\theta)$ is now a quantity dependent on the Lode's angle according to Argyris et al. (1974):

$$M(\theta) = \frac{2c}{(1+c) - (1-c) \cdot \cos(3\theta)} M_c \quad (23)$$

with $c = M_e/M_c$, in which M_c is the stress ratio at Critical State in triaxial compression and M_e is the stress ratio at Critical State in triaxial extension.

The Lode's angle can be determined using:

$$\cos(3\theta) = \sqrt{6} \cdot \text{tr}(\bar{\mathbf{n}}^3) \quad (24)$$

with

$$\bar{\mathbf{n}} = \frac{\bar{\mathbf{r}} - \alpha}{\sqrt{(\bar{\mathbf{r}} - \alpha) : (\bar{\mathbf{r}} - \alpha)}} \quad (25)$$

and where $\theta = 0^\circ$ corresponds to triaxial compression and $\theta = 60^\circ$ corresponds to triaxial extension.

The gradients of the plastic potential are given by:

$$\frac{\partial G}{\partial \sigma} = 3(\bar{s} - \bar{p}\alpha) + \frac{1}{3}\bar{p} \cdot \left(M^2 - \frac{3}{2}\bar{\mathbf{r}} : \bar{\mathbf{r}} \right) \mathbf{I} + \frac{\partial G}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \sigma} \quad (26)$$

where

$$\frac{\partial G}{\partial \theta} = 6M^2 \cdot \bar{p}(p_0 - \bar{p}) \cdot \frac{(1-c) \sin(3\theta)}{(1+c) - (1-c) \cos(3\theta)} \quad (27)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \sigma} = \frac{-3 \left[\bar{\mathbf{n}}^2 - \text{tr}(\bar{\mathbf{n}}^3)\bar{\mathbf{n}} - 1/3 \cdot \mathbf{I} \cdot \left(1 + \text{tr}(\bar{\mathbf{n}}^2\alpha) - \text{tr}(\bar{\mathbf{n}}^3) \cdot \text{tr}(\bar{\mathbf{n}}\alpha) \right) \right]}{\bar{p} \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} (\bar{\mathbf{r}} - \alpha) : (\bar{\mathbf{r}} - \alpha) \cdot \sin(3\theta)} \quad (28)$$

5. Plastic behaviour

The following quantity related to isotropic hardening is introduced:

$$\bar{p}_0 = \frac{\partial G}{\partial p} \cdot p_0 \cdot \frac{\nu}{\lambda - \kappa} = \text{tr} \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial \sigma} \right) \cdot p_0 \cdot \frac{\nu}{\lambda - \kappa} \quad (29)$$

while the equivalent for rotational hardening is given by:

$$\bar{\alpha} = \frac{\nu}{\lambda - \kappa} \cdot C \cdot \left(\frac{p}{p_0} \right)^2 \left| \text{tr} \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial \sigma} \right) \right| \cdot \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} (\bar{\mathbf{r}} - x \cdot \alpha) : (\bar{\mathbf{r}} - x \cdot \alpha) \cdot (\alpha^b - \alpha)} \quad (30)$$

where

$$\alpha^b = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \cdot \min(N, M_e) \cdot \mathbf{n}_x \quad (31)$$

and

$$\mathbf{n}_x = \frac{\left(\frac{\bar{\mathbf{r}}}{x}\right) - \alpha}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{\bar{\mathbf{r}}}{x} - \alpha\right) : \left(\frac{\bar{\mathbf{r}}}{x} - \alpha\right)}} \quad (32)$$

The hardening modulus for states on the bounding surface can be determined using:

$$\bar{A} = -\left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial p_0} \bar{p}_0 + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \alpha} : \bar{\alpha}\right) \quad (33)$$

with

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial p_0} = -\bar{p} \left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2} \alpha : \alpha\right) \quad (34)$$

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial \alpha} = -3\bar{p}(\bar{s} - p_0 \alpha) \quad (35)$$

The current value of the hardening modulus can then be determined through an additional correction:

$$A = \bar{A} + \frac{h \cdot p_0^3}{\langle \frac{b}{b-1} - s_Y \rangle} \quad (36)$$

where b is defined as outlined above under *Projection rule*, s_Y is a parameter defining the size of the elastic locus (larger values of s_Y mean the denominator is negative and hence taken as 0, which leads to $A \rightarrow \infty$ and thus to $\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p \rightarrow 0$) and h is dependent on the hardening parameter d :

$$h = \frac{h_0}{1+d} \quad (37)$$

The plastic multiplier can be obtained using:

$$\Lambda = \frac{\frac{\partial F^T}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} [D] \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}{\frac{\partial F^T}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} [D] \frac{\partial G}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} + A} \quad (38)$$

5. Hardening rules

5.1. Isotropic hardening

The hardening rule controlling the change in the size of the bounding surface is given as:

$$\Delta p_o = \Delta \varepsilon_{vol}^p \cdot p_0 \cdot \frac{\nu}{\lambda - \kappa} = \langle \Lambda \rangle \frac{\partial G}{\partial p} \cdot p_0 \cdot \frac{\nu}{\lambda - \kappa} = \langle \Lambda \rangle \cdot tr \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \right) \cdot p_0 \cdot \frac{\nu}{\lambda - \kappa} \quad (39)$$

which can be rewritten as:

$$\Delta p_o = \langle \Lambda \rangle \cdot \bar{p}_0 \quad (38)$$

5.2. Rotational hardening

The kinematic hardening is controlled by:

$$\Delta \boldsymbol{\alpha} = \langle \Lambda \rangle \frac{\nu}{\lambda - \kappa} \cdot C \cdot \left(\frac{p}{p_0} \right)^2 \left| \text{tr} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{G}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \right) \right| \cdot \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} (\bar{\mathbf{r}} - x \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}) : (\bar{\mathbf{r}} - x \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha})} \cdot (\boldsymbol{\alpha}^b - \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \quad (39)$$

and can be rewritten as:

$$\Delta \boldsymbol{\alpha} = \langle \Lambda \rangle \cdot \bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} \quad (40)$$

5.3. Projection centre evolution

Following Seidalinov (2018), the projection centre updates at each stress reversal and evolves with bounding surface evolution to ensure consistency.

Condition for stress reversal detection is defined as $\Lambda \leq 0$. In this case, a new Projection Centre is created and set such that it takes the coordinates of the current stress point:

$$p_c = p \quad (41)$$

$$\mathbf{s}_c = \mathbf{s} \quad (42)$$

Moreover, to accommodate the evolution of p_0 and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$, in the absence of stress reversal, the evolution of the position of the projection centre is determined as:

$$\Delta p_c = \frac{p_c}{p_0} \cdot \Delta p_0 \quad (43)$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{s}_c = \frac{\mathbf{s}_c}{p_0} \cdot \Delta p_0 + \left[p_c \cdot \Delta \boldsymbol{\alpha} - X \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \cdot \frac{p_c \cdot (p_0 - p_c) \cdot \frac{3}{2}}{\sqrt{\left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2} \boldsymbol{\alpha} : \boldsymbol{\alpha} \right) \cdot p_c \cdot (p_0 - p_c)}} \mathbf{n}_c \right] \quad (44)$$

with X being a scalar quantity evaluated as:

$$X = \frac{\left[\frac{3}{2} (\mathbf{s}_c - \mathbf{s}_\alpha) : (\mathbf{s}_c - \mathbf{s}_\alpha) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\left[\frac{3}{2} (\mathbf{s}_b - \mathbf{s}_\alpha) : (\mathbf{s}_b - \mathbf{s}_\alpha) \right]} \quad (45)$$

where \mathbf{s}_b is a deviatoric stress tensor on the bounding surface along

$$\mathbf{n}_c = \frac{\mathbf{s}_c - \mathbf{s}_\alpha}{|\mathbf{s}_c - \mathbf{s}_\alpha|} \quad (46)$$

for a given PC and $\mathbf{s}_\alpha = p_c \boldsymbol{\alpha}$.

5.4. Damage

The damage parameter evolves according to:

$$\Delta d = a_d \varepsilon_q^{p*} \quad (47)$$

where ε_q^{p*} is a scalar quantity representing the cumulative deviatoric plastic strain:

$$\varepsilon_q^{p*} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{e}^p : \Delta \mathbf{e}^p} \quad (48)$$

with $\Delta \mathbf{e}^p = \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p - \Delta \varepsilon_{vol}^p / 3 \cdot \mathbf{I}_3$ representing the deviatoric plastic strain tensor.

5.5. Destructuration

If $P26 > 0$ and $P28 > 1$, the model accounts for structure effects and destructuration. The adopted framework follows the approach by Taiebat et al. (2010), in which intrinsic and structured surfaces are used to describe the reconstituted (i.e., structureless) and structured states, respectively. In this framework, the state variable $p_{0,i}$ is introduced to represent the size of the intrinsic bounding surface and is related to p_0 through the sensitivity parameter S_i as follows:

$$p_{0,i} = \frac{p_0}{S_i} \quad (49)$$

The hardening rule controlling the evolution of the size of the intrinsic bounding surface is similar to Eq. (39), as such:

$$\Delta p_{0i} = \Delta \varepsilon_{vol}^p \cdot p_{0i} \cdot \frac{v}{\lambda - \kappa} = \langle \Lambda \rangle \cdot \bar{p}_{0i} = \langle \Lambda \rangle \cdot tr \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{G}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \right) \cdot p_{0i} \cdot \frac{v}{\lambda - \kappa} \quad (50)$$

Furthermore, the evolution of the sensitivity parameter is governed by the following hardening law:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta S_i &= -A k_i \left(\frac{1+e}{\lambda - \kappa} \right) (S_i - S_b) \sqrt{(1-a)(\Delta \varepsilon_v^p)^2 + a(\Delta \varepsilon_q^p)^2} = \langle \Lambda \rangle \cdot \bar{S}_i \\ &= -\langle \Lambda \rangle k_i \left(\frac{1+e}{\lambda - \kappa} \right) (S_i - S_b) \sqrt{(1-a) \left[tr \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{G}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \right) \right]^2 + a \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{G}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \right)' : \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{G}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \right)'} \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

where A is the activation mechanism discussed in the next section, the quantities a , S_b and k_i are material parameters, while $\left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{G}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \right)'$ and $tr \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{G}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \right)$ represent the deviatoric and volumetric components of $\frac{\partial \mathbf{G}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}$, respectively. Compared to the formulation by Taiebat et al. (2010), the parameter S_b is introduced similar to Baudet and Stallebrass (2004) to represent the ultimate sensitivity characterizing the destructured state.

Finally, the hardening rule controlling the evolution of the size of the structured bounding surface is:

$$\Delta p_o = \langle \Lambda \rangle \cdot \bar{p}_o = \langle \Lambda \rangle (S_i \bar{p}_{0,i} + \bar{S}_i \bar{p}_{0,i}) \quad (52)$$

5.6. Activation

Eq. (51) includes the activation mechanism proposed by Palmieri and Taiebat (2024) defined as:

$$A = H(b_{sr}^{thr} - b_{sr}) \quad (53)$$

where b_{sr} is a state variable representing the value of b updated at the last stress reversal, while b_{sr}^{thr} is a model parameter representing its threshold. The Heaviside step function $H(x)$ ensures that $A = 0$ for non-positive arguments ($x \leq 0$) and $A = 1$ for positive arguments ($x > 0$).

In this mechanism, the variable b_{sr} is used as a proxy for the cyclic stress amplitude, while parameter b_{sr}^{thr} represents its threshold. In combination with the destructuration law, when $b_{sr} > b_{sr}^{thr}$, the activation mechanism prevents destructuration ($A = 0$). Conversely, when $b_{sr} < b_{sr}^{thr}$, the occurrence of destructuration remains unaltered ($A = 1$). This mechanism can be used to simulate cyclic degradation only when the cyclic shear stress amplitude exceeds a defined threshold.

6. Initialisation

The axis of the bounding surface is initialised by setting it to coincide with the initial stress state, i.e:

$$\alpha = \frac{s}{p} = \frac{\sigma - pI}{p} \quad (54)$$

The size of the bounding surface can then be determined based on the parameters defining OCR:

$-1 \leq OCR < 0$ and $0 < OCR < 1$: Not possible.

OCR = 0: The initialisation is based on information provided via a text file with the following format:

Location: `C:\icmage\input.icmageM18.txt`

Format:

<i>Ndata</i>	<i>Ctype</i>	<i>Ntype</i>
<i>Coord1</i>	<i>Data1</i>	
<i>Coord2</i>	<i>Data2</i>	
...		
<i>CoordN</i>	<i>DataN</i>	

where *Ndata* is the number of points given, *Ctype* is the switch defining which coordinate is being given in the list below (*Ctype* = 0 for *x*, *Ctype* = 1 for *y* and *Ctype* = 2 for *z*), while *Ntype* determines whether the data given relates to OCR in terms of p' (*Ntype* = 0) or OCR in terms of σ'_v (*Ntype* = 1).

Based on the specified value of OCR, the following operations are carried out:

OCR = 1: The initial stress state is on the bounding surface.

If $K_0 = 1$, then $p_0 = p_{ini}$.

If $K_0 \neq 1$, then to calculate p_0 the current stress state needs to be substituted into the equation for the bounding surface (i.e. the initial stress state corresponds to the projected stress state), which can then be solved for p_0 :

$$F = \frac{3}{2}(\mathbf{s}_{ini} - p_{ini}\boldsymbol{\alpha}) : (\mathbf{s}_{ini} - p_{ini}\boldsymbol{\alpha}) - \left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2}\boldsymbol{\alpha} : \boldsymbol{\alpha}\right) \cdot p_{ini}(p_0 - p_{ini}) = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow p_0 = p_{ini} + \frac{\frac{3}{2}(\mathbf{s}_{ini} - p_{ini}\boldsymbol{\alpha}) : (\mathbf{s}_{ini} - p_{ini}\boldsymbol{\alpha})}{\left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2}\boldsymbol{\alpha} : \boldsymbol{\alpha}\right) \cdot p_{ini}} \quad (55)$$

OCR > 1: $p_0 = OCR \cdot p_{ini}$.

OCR < -1: $\sigma_{v,max} = OCR \cdot \sigma_{v,ini}$, where $\sigma_{v,ini}$ is the current vertical effective stress and $\sigma_{v,max}$ is the maximum vertical effective stress. To complete the characterisation of the stress state at maximum vertical effective stress, the horizontal effective needs to be calculated:

$$\sigma_{h,max} = (1 - \sin \varphi) \cdot \sigma_{v,max} \quad (56)$$

This stress state is then introduced into the expression for the bounding surface to determine its size.

OCR can vary with depth as shown in Figure 1, where the coordinate used to characterise this variation is defined by *P16 DepthSwitch*. If *P16* is set to 0.0, then the variation is along x_c , if *P16* is set to 1.0, then the variation is along y_c and if *P16* is set to 2.0, then the variation is along z_c (3D analyses only).

Figure 1: Variation of OCR with depth.

The void ratio is initialised based on the value of e_0 provided by *P17* if this is a positive value. If negative, then $v_1 = -P17$ and the void ratio is initialised as follows:

If $OCR = 1$, i.e. the stress state is on the isotropic virgin compression line, then:

$$v = v_1 - \lambda \cdot \ln p \quad (57)$$

In every other permissible case, the stress state is on a swelling line and:

$$v = v_1 - \lambda \cdot \ln p_0 + \kappa \cdot (\ln p_0 - \ln p) \quad (58)$$

To avoid singularities, the projection centre is initialised to 99% of the initial stress conditions, i.e. $p_c = 0.99 \cdot p_{ini}$ and $s_c = 0.99 \cdot s_{ini}$. This creates a sufficiently large distance between the projection centre and the current stress state to enable the determination of the projection point, without triggering excessive plasticity within the first loading steps.

The b_{sr} value is initialized equal to 1, assuming the last stress reversal at OCR=1.

MODEL USAGE

1. *P21 OutputControl* determines the level of output desired from the model integration:

$P21 = 0$	Full output with details on the integration of the model and warnings (default).
$P21 = 1$	Full output with details on the integration of the model but without warnings.
$P21 = 2$	Brief output consisting only of the progress of the calculation (step and iteration) and warnings.
$P21 = 3$	Brief output consisting only of the progress of the calculation (step and iteration) but without warnings.
$P21 = 4$	No output will be produced

2. If *P22 EnergyCalc* is set to 1.0, the UMIP will add 33 new hardening parameters to the constitutive model to calculate and store energy-related quantities. More information can be found in the documentation of the UMIP but of greatest interest are the current damping ratio (HP76), the secant shear stiffness (HP77) and the secant bulk stiffness (HP78). This module is particularly useful if the model is being used for pseudo-static or dynamic analyses. Note that the use of this option increases slightly memory and processing requirements.

3. A text file input approach is available to define values of parameters which could not be included in the list of parameters due to PLAXIS' limit of 50 model parameters. To use this feature, a file called *M18.settings.txt* should be placed within the folder *C:\icmage* with the following contents:

Control parameter			Default value	Description
F01	<i>MinPlasticSteps</i>	≥ 0	2	Minimum no of plastic integration steps
F02	<i>MaxPlasticSteps</i>	≥ 0	10000	Maximum no of plastic integration steps
F03	<i>PlasticTol</i>	≥ 0	1×10^{-3}	Plastic integration tolerance
F04	<i>PlasticHPControl</i>	0,1	1	0 – changes in elastic hardening parameters do not affect elastic integration 1 – changes in elastic hardening parameters affect elastic integration
F05	<i>YieldTol</i>	≥ 0	1×10^{-6}	Yield tolerance
F06	<i>ApexTol (FL⁻²)</i>	≥ 0	0.1	Apex tolerance
F07	<i>YieldMax</i>	≥ 0	1000.0	Maximum value of yield function
F08	<i>PlasticUnload</i>	≥ 0	1×10^{-6}	Plastic unloading tolerance
F09	<i>Solution Control</i>	0,1	1	0 – the stiffness matrix is generated only at the start of the phase 1 – the stiffness matrix is generated at the start of every step

Control parameter			Default value	Description
F10	<i>Stiffness scalar</i>	≥ 10	120	Scalar used to increase the elastic matrix in percentage. Larger values improve the stability of the solution but slows down convergence.
F11	<i>Unloading control</i>	0,1	0	0 – the stiffness matrix is generated based on current elastic stiffness 1 – the stiffness matrix is generated based on maximum elastic stiffness
F12	<i>Undrained ν</i>	$-1.0 \leq \nu < 0.5$	0.495	Undrained Poisson's ratio to use
F13	<i>Debug switch</i>	0,1	0	0 – no additional debug information 1 – full debug information (note that this will generate very large output files)

Note that, with the exception of F04, F09 and F11, if a value of zero is used, then the default value (or the one in the graphical input if it has been specified) will be used. Since a value of 0 is a possible value for F04, F09 and F11, the desired value must always be specified. Moreover, the file must always have the full list of parameters being given as the code expects to find a column with 12 values, returning an error if a smaller number of parameters is found. Lastly, **note that parameters specified via the GUI will always take precedence.**

CALIBRATION

The calibration of the IC MAGE M18 model should begin with the basic SANICLAY parameters, using monotonic test data as described by Dafalias et al. (2006). The additional components, i.e., small-strain stiffness, bounding surface, damage, destructuration and activation, should be calibrated sequentially and only if required by the observed behaviour, in accordance with the model's hierarchical formulation.

The following focuses on the calibration of additional components using experimental data for Cloverdale Clay (Zergoun and Vaid, 1994). This natural clay was subjected to undrained cyclic triaxial loading at isotropic confining pressure of 200 kPa and OCR = 1, with a constant cyclic stress ratio (CSR = q_{cyc}/s_u , with $s_u = 56$ kPa). The tests revealed a cyclic stress threshold at CSR = 0.55, beyond which significant stiffness and post-cyclic strength degradation were observed, along with excess pore pressure accumulation (Zergoun, 1991). Oedometer test further indicates that destructuration initiates at a vertical effective stress of approximately 95 kPa.

To model the cyclic response of Cloverdale Clay, destructuration is adopted as the primary degradation mechanism, while damage is not employed ($P8 = 0$). This choice allows to simulate excess pore pressure accumulation and strength loss, coupled with stiffness degradation. In addition, the activation mechanism is used to reproduce the observed CSR threshold. A summary of the calibrated model parameters is provided in the table below.

Table. IC-MAGE M18 material parameters for Cloverdale clay

P1: μ	P2: λ	P3: κ	P4: M_c	P5: M_e	P6: N	P7: h_0
0	0.21	0.03	1.29	1.27	1	100
P8: a_d	P9: C	P10: x	P11: s_y	P18: K_{min}	P22: p_r	P23: A
0	3	1.73	1	0	1	550
P24: n	P25: m	P26: k_i	P27: a	P29: S_b	P30: b_{sr}^{thr}	
0.77	0.23	0.55	0.5	1.3	1.35	

7.1 Small-strain stiffness

Parameters P22-P25 are calibrated to reproduce the initial shear modulus G_0 and its dependence on mean effective stress and OCR. In the absence of test data, parameters P23, P24 and P25 can be estimated using empirical correlations with the Plasticity Index (PI), as proposed by Viggiani and Atkinson (1995), with $P22 = 1$ kPa.

For Cloverdale clay, P23 is set 550 to reproduce $G_0 = 32$ MPa, while P22, P24 and P25 are derived based on a PI of 24, in accordance with the Viggiani and Atkinson (1995) correlations.

7.2 Bounding surface

The bounding surface parameter P11 is set to 1 to define a null size of the elastic nucleus. Parameter P7 controls the non-linear elastic behaviour and should be calibrated using cyclic test data at small shear strain amplitudes, where stiffness degradation is negligible. Figure 2 illustrates the influence of P7 on the cyclic stress–strain response. These results are obtained in the absence of degradation ($k_i = 0$).

Figure 2: Influence of bounding surface parameter P7 (h_0) on cyclic stress strain response.

Alternatively, P7 can be estimated based on modulus reduction and damping curves. Finally, this parameter could be also estimated based on monotonic test data, although this approach does not allow assessment of the model’s ability to reproduce hysteretic damping.

7.3 Activation

Parameter P30 can be calibrated based on simulations results. These simulations should be performed with all model parameters defined, while enforcing inactive destructuration (i.e., setting $k_i = 0$).

With inactive destructuration, simulations at constant CSR result in the state variable b_{sr} stabilising to a constant value after a number of cycles. This constant value decreases as CSR increases. To prevent destructuration at CSRs below the threshold, P30 should set lower than the constant b_{sr} value obtained in simulation at the highest CSR of interest below threshold.

Figure 3 illustrates the evolution of b_{sr} for CSR = 0.54 leading to the selection of P30 = 1.35.

Figure 3: Variation of state variable b_{sr} during simulation of CSR = 0.54

7.4 Destructuration

Destructuration parameters P26 and P29 should be calibrated using results from both monotonic and cyclic loading tests. Figures 4 and 5 illustrate the influence of the destructuration parameters P26 and P29 during undrained triaxial and isotropic compression tests, respectively. In these simulations, P28 is set equal to 2.0, while P27 is assumed equal to 0.5.

Figure 4: Influence of destructuration parameters P26 and P29 during undrained monotonic triaxial.

Figure 5: Influence of destructuration parameters P26 and P29 during isotropic compression.

In addition, the effect of parameters P26 and P29 during cyclic loading is shown in Figures 6 and 7, respectively, which show the accumulated axial strains with cycles at two different levels of CSR. Parameter P26 tends to uniformly affects the rate of destructuration across different cyclic amplitudes, while P29 primarily affects the response at lower amplitudes.

Figure 6: Influence of destructuration parameter P26 during cyclic triaxial test at different CRSs.

Figure 7: Influence of destructuration parameter P29 during cyclic triaxial test at different CRSs.

VALIDATION

8.1 Oedometer test

Figures 8 assesses the model's ability to reproduce the compressibility of Cloverdale Clay during oedometer test. For this simulation, initial conditions were $p = 10 \text{ kPa}$, $q = 0$, $e_0 = 1.4$, $\text{OCR} = 8$, and $S_{i0} = 2.5$. In the absence of tests on reconstituted specimen, value of S_{i0} was assumed based on the available test results.

Figure 8: Comparison between simulation and experiments during oedometer test for Cloverdale Clay

8.2 Undrained monotonic triaxial compression and extension

Figures 9 assesses the model's ability to reproduce the undrained triaxial response of Cloverdale Clay with initial conditions: $p=200 \text{ kPa}$, $q=0$, $e_0=1.0$, $\text{OCR} = 1$, and $S_{i0} = 2.08$. Value of S_{i0} was derived based on simulation results of isotropic compression test starting from initial conditions used in Section 8.1.

Figure 9: Comparison between simulation and experiments during undrained monotonic triaxial compression and extension for Cloverdale Clay

8.3 Undrained cyclic triaxial compression

Figures 10 and 11 assess the model's ability to reproduce the cyclic response of Cloverdale Clay in undrained cyclic triaxial compression tests, with initial conditions as in Section 8.2.

Figure 10: Comparison between simulation and experiments during undrained cyclic triaxial test: stress-strain response at CSR = 0.79 (a) and 0.46 (b).

Figure 11: Comparison between simulations and experiments during undrained cyclic triaxial test: accumulated axial strain with cycles at different CSRs.

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